

Data Stewardship in Germany 2024: First Steps Towards a Stronger Community

Daniela Hausen, Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9083-0670>

Stefano Della Chiesa, Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6693-2199>

Jens Dierkes, University of Cologne, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0121-9261>

Stefan Kirsch, Ernst Abbe University of Applied Sciences Jena, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0638-4639>

Hans März, Protestant University of Applied Sciences Bochum, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4013-7717>

Dzulia Terzijska, Braunschweig University of Technology, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1698-6826>

Ute Trautwein-Bruns, RWTH Aachen University, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0531-0182>

Jürgen Windeck, Technical University of Darmstadt, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1909-4353>

Abstract

The role of data stewards as key players in research data management (RDM) is becoming increasingly important. Nevertheless, there is still a lack of a clear definition, institutional anchoring and a networked community for this professional group in Germany. Against this background, the third workshop 'Data Stewardship goes Germany' (DSgG) took place in 2024, building on previous initiatives and specifically promoting the development of a data steward community in Germany. The core of the workshop was the application of the Community Canvas model to jointly develop the values, goals, tasks and structures of such a network. The results show a clear need for exchange, mutual support and professionalisation. Trust, openness and diversity were identified as core values; concrete formats such as a buddy system, storytelling rituals and a central communication platform are planned. Three thematic working groups were established to systematically work on strategic goals, communication channels ('yellow pages') and key challenges faced by data stewards. The establishment of a sustainable, collaborative community should strengthen the visibility and effectiveness of data stewards in research institutions and contribute to improved RDM practice in the sense of Open Science in the long term.

Introduction

In 2016, the German Council for Information Infrastructures (RfII) stated that the digital transformation has reached the scientific community and needs to be actively shaped. Research data management (RDM) is seen as a key function for optimising the use of research data at the end and beginning of a project or scientific work¹. Researchers can be supported in their RDM in a number of ways, for example through the use of user-friendly and intuitive tools, but also through personal support from local RDM competence centres or data stewards. While local RDM competence centres have been established at most German universities and non-university research institutions in recent years, it can be observed that the use of data stewards is still rather rudimentary². This may be due to the fact that there is still no clear and standardised definition of data stewards and that data stewardship as a research-supporting activity is still a very young branch³.

The first profiles for data stewards - competencies, focus and training - were created in 2021 for the life sciences in the Netherlands and in 2022⁴ in Germany with the *DataStew* project⁵, the results and *DataStew* profiles of which have been incorporated into Elixir's RDMkit⁶.

In addition, the results of the *DataStew* project were presented in the keynote speech at the *Data Stewardship goes Germany (DSgG) 2023* workshop and, like the other six exciting talks and 21 poster presentations, highlighted the different facets of the topic. Contributions ranged from practical tools to strategic considerations for institutional embedding. A central, recurring theme was the discrepancy between ideal and current practice in research data management. The contributions presented a variety of approaches and tools to bridge this gap and emphasised the crucial role of RDM professionals - especially data stewards - in the entire life cycle of research data.

The Barcamp sessions of workshop 2023 focused on topics such as job titles, tasks and roles, institutional anchoring, qualifications and the development of a network of data stewards. Three aspects became very clear during these sessions and in the concluding discussion:

- There is currently no data steward community, but there is a desire for one.
- The term 'data steward' needs to be defined more precisely and the tasks of a data steward need to be clearly defined and brought to life.

¹ RfII-Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen (2016), Herausgeber. Leistung aus Vielfalt: Empfehlungen zu Strukturen, Prozessen und Finanzierung des Forschungsdatenmanagements in Deutschland. 2016, <https://d-nb.info/1104292440/34>

² Steinke, B., Hausen, D., Kuberek, M., Hora, M., Kessler, K., Kramer, C., ... Strötgen, R. (2022). Data Stewards an den TU9-Universitäten – Bestandsaufnahme, Handlungsfelder und Kooperationspotenzial. *Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement*, (1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2022.1.8364>

³ Jetten, M. (2021, Juli 12). Professionalising the data steward roles in the Netherlands. FAIR data stewardship capacity building & the role of communities. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5091300>

⁴ Jetten, M., Grootveld, M., Mordant, A., Jansen, M., Bloemers, M., Miedema, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>

⁵ Seidlmayer, E., Hoffmann, F., Dierkes, J., Lindstädt, B., Depping, R., Förstner, K.U. (2023). Forschung unterstützen – Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen: Ergebnisse des Projektes DataStew. *Publisso*. <https://repository.publisso.de/resource/frl:6441397>

⁶ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_steward (last check: 2025-03-24)

- Collaboration of data stewards with universities and/ or non-university research institutions centralised RDM teams on the one hand and researchers on the other hand is necessary.

In order to begin to address these issues, the mailing list datastewardsgermany@listserv.dfn.de has been set up. It quickly became apparent that further progress would not be possible without involving the community. As a result, DSgG 2024 was used to deepen the understanding of community needs.⁷ To support this, the Community Canvas model was applied—an approach successfully used by Oset Garcia et al. (2023) in Flanders for community building and development.⁸

Identifying Needs with the Community Canvas

In order to establish a broad consensus across participants and future members, we used the Community Canvas⁹ to discuss the shape of a future data steward Network. The Community Canvas was developed to help forming sustainable communities. The canvas focuses on three aspects: 1) Identity, 2) Experience and 3) Structure, which are broken down into 17 themes where each consists of several questions. The canvas material provides sub questions as well as summaries to guide discussion through the different aspects.

Figure 1: The community canvas overview. Identity themes in blue, Experiences in red and Structure aspects in green. Source: screenshot of community-canvas.org

⁷ Hausen, D. A., Jaek, A., Kaulbach, L.-L., and Lennartz, T. (2024). Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024. Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024 (DSgG2024), Aachen. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14191227>

⁸ Oset García, P., Van den Eynden, V., Choueiki, Z., and Acar, T. Building a Community of Data Stewards in Flanders: Lessons Learned from the FRDN Knowledge Hub's Experience with the Community Canvas Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10039571>.

⁹ Pfortmüller, F., Luchsinger, N., Mombartz, S. (2017) The Community Canvas Guidebook. The Guide to build meaningful communities. <https://community-canvas.org/>

The canvas was successfully tested with a smaller group prior to the DSgG workshop to see if it would be useful. For the DSgG, the different themes were discussed in group sessions. Not all themes could be discussed in-depth, but all topics were addressed. The data from the Community Canvas sessions are published on Zenodo¹⁰.

Identity

The identity section asks about the why, the goals and values. It defines the culture of the community and includes the themes:

- **Purpose** - Why does the community exist?
- **Member Identity** - Who is the community for?
- **Values** - What is important to us as a community?
- **Success Definition** - How does the community define success?
- **Brand** - How does the community express itself?

One fundamental question was already raised during the 2023's workshop in Dresden¹¹: Do we need another RDM community in Germany? Over the past years several communities have been built, e.g. the DINI/Nestor AG Forschungsdaten, state initiatives, NFDI consortia, working groups, sections, and task areas, as well as tool-focused communities, e.g. for RDMO, ELNs, and others. Is there additional need for a network focusing on data stewards, and who is considered to be part of the network?

Purpose. A network is built to share knowledge and to get to know people. This is especially important for new data stewards. In our group discussions, the onboarding support was mentioned as a general purpose of the network. New data stewards need an overview of topics, tools, initiatives, projects, and people. The network should also be a safe place to talk about RDM challenges, pitfalls and errors, a chance to exchange information on and experience with services, and also provide emotional support. As a community of practice, it should develop best practices, standards and terminologies, and offer a chance to learn from each other.

Member identity. The community includes all those who see themselves as data stewards, who are motivated, who seek cooperation rather than competition and who are open to support and help each other. Data stewards support scientists in a dynamic environment. The community is looking for people who are agents of change, service-oriented, from a variety of fields, ideas and backgrounds.

Values. To pursue the idea of an open network, diverse perspectives and ideas are as important as transparency, inclusiveness and service orientation. The willingness to share experiences, both good/best practices as well as failures will build trust, establish a culture of learning and foster the value of the network for all members.

¹⁰ Hausen, D. A., Windeck, J., Schönau, S., & Dierkes, J. (2025). Results of the Community Canvas Sessions – Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024. Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024 (DSgG 2024), Aachen. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112753>

¹¹ Krause, M., Rümmler, A., Zinke, K., Little, J., & Würzner, K.-M. (2024). Data Stewardship goes Germany (DSgG), Dresden/Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10514268>

Success Definition. When brainstorming about the ideal community, participants are looking for a sustainable, supportive and active community that is also fun to engage with. The interaction shall include onboarding, sharing resources, a buddy system for new members and also sub-groups of special interest. The network benefits from diverse backgrounds, skill sets, experiences and contact. Co-authoring publications or networking with other initiatives is described as successful.

Brand. Data steward communities have been established in several countries like the Netherlands. Data stewards are seen as bridge builders, translators and guides¹² which were also addressed by the participating data stewards. A more in-depth discussion is still open.

Experience

The experience section deals with the experience of members within the community and how this can be cultivated.

- **Selection** - How do people join the community?
- **Transition** - How do members leave the community?
- **Shared Experiences** - What experiences do members share?
- **Rituals** - What rituals happen regularly?
- **Content** - What content creates value for members?
- **Rules** - What are the community's rules?
- **Roles** - What roles can members play?

Selection. Member selection refers to the process by which data stewards join the community. It was discussed that the community should be as open as possible, as closed as necessary. While anyone who identifies as a data steward should be able to join, membership should primarily consist of persons who are active in data stewardship regardless of their perspective on the topic, to ensure alignment with the community's shared goals and vision. Data stewards perceive significant value in being part of the community and benefit from their participation. As a result, they actively seek engagement, for example, by subscribing to the mailing list¹³. Targeted promotion at events and other outreach efforts are essential to raise awareness of the community among the intended audience. In the early stages, identifying core members with the resources, motivation and commitment to take on responsibility can be crucial to the successful establishment and development of the community.

Transition. Transition refers to how members leave the community. The discussion emphasised that there should be no active exclusion of members unless they break community rules. However, the activity of the members can naturally have a certain dynamic, as the roles, interests, and available resources of data stewards may change over time.

Shared Experiences. Shared Experiences are at the core of the community from the members' perspective. A key focus of the discussion was challenges and practices, because sharing experiences is a fundamental need for all data stewards. This includes not only epic

¹² Rothfritz, L. (2019). Data Stewardship als Boundary-Work. *edoc - Open-Access-Publikationsserver der Humboldt-Universität*. <https://doi.org/10.18452/20636>

¹³ datastewardsgermany@listserv.dfn.de

failures and lessons learned but also shared ideas and an overview of available services, such as a map of Germany or the yellow pages for RDM. The knowledge exchange aims to facilitate the development of solutions to problems, while collaboration within the community helps bridge gaps and improve efficiency.

Rituals & Traditions. Rituals and traditions are recurrent activities that serve to strengthen the sense of community. The DSgG annual conference has become such a ritual and also coined the term “Data Stewardship goes Germany”. Regular online meetings, such as a monthly Jour Fixe, were also identified as recurring elements. Storytelling formats such as Meme of the Month and Scary Tales promote an open failure culture and facilitate the exchange of experiences.

Content. Important content that creates value for the members of the data steward community in Germany includes the sharing of experiences, which enables members to learn from each other’s challenges and solutions. The exchange of good/best practices and the discussion of shared problems enhance collaboration and provide opportunities for collective problem-solving. Thinking ahead by sharing visions for shaping the future was particularly named as valuable content.

Membership Rules. The membership rules of the community include clear expectations for both members and the community itself, fostering active participation and respectful behavior. At a later stage, this will be taken up and discussed again.

Membership Roles. The data stewards identified various roles within the community, which are determined by the level of involvement and experience of the members. These roles can be categorized into active and passive participants, including members who regularly engage in community activities, contributors and disseminators who actively share knowledge and resources, and consumers who primarily seek to receive information and benefit from the content shared by others. Additionally, members may assume mentoring roles as either mentors or mentees, and engage in working groups as either participants or leaders. There are also board members who guide the overall direction of the community, while the distinction between newcomers and long-term members highlights different levels of experience and engagement within the community.

Structure

The structure aspect of the canvas addresses the practical and organisational elements that support and sustain the operation of a community. It defines the rules, governance, resources, and tools that ensure stability and scalability while enabling effective interactions among members:

- **Organisation** - Who runs the community?
- **Governance** - How are decisions made in the community?
- **Financing** - What is the community’s plan to be financially sustainable?
- **Channels & Platforms** - What channels does the community use to communicate and gather?
- **Data Management** - How does the community manage the data of its members?

These aspects are fundamental to the effective organization and operation of a community. While the participants agreed that a network specifically for data stewards and related individuals could benefit the community, and valuable ideas and suggestions were generated for each question, it quickly became clear that the resources and funding to make such a network a reality are not readily available.

Organisation. For the organisation of the community, inspiration is taken from public and social associations. The community is led by a group of decision-makers, with a structure that adapts to different activities, which are current and relevant to the group. The group of decision-makers are members who are elected and rotate in order to share and divide responsibility and workload. A moderator supports coordination, while leadership is driven by intrinsic motivation, self-commitment, and community engagement. The organisational framework of the community includes working groups with defined topics and responsibilities. The network follows the principle of activation energy to sustain engagement.

Governance. Governance is maintained through a board and committees, ensuring a low level of hierarchy. A Code of Conduct guides interactions and decision-making processes.

Financing. Since financing is difficult, it may be easier to realise the launch and initial operation in the first years of the community as a project. Short and long-term funding sources could include grants from networks and organisations such as NFDI, EOSC, RDA, and FAIRimpact, as well as membership and event fees. Additional financial support may come from foundations like Stifterverband and the Volkswagen Foundation. These are initial ideas that will need to be followed up and evaluated over time.

Channels & Platforms. Since the main part of a community is to create an environment for the members to interact and communicate with each other, there were a lot of suggestions for possible tools. Communication and collaboration could take place via mailing lists, websites, wikis, social media, and various chat platforms (Mattermost, Slack, Rocket.Chat, Q&A platforms). Existing RDM-community platforms could also be utilised. While the workshop participants gathered a wide range of options, the final choice should take into account functionality, security aspects, as well as sustainable and easy long-term operation.

Data Management. The community's technical setup for the management of the data of the members could include a website, servers, and multiple communication channels, ensuring structured and secure data management. It is important to select the right ones and protect the data in accordance with the existing guidelines. One part of this aspect, namely the channels, is being addressed by a working group.

The Results of the Community Canvas

The Community Canvas explored what defines our community, its values, and its purpose, with inclusion and trust as core values. Participants envision a community of data stewards with a high value placed on onboarding, knowledge sharing, and peer-to-peer support. Similar to other emerging online communities, this envisioned community aims to provide a trusted space to discuss challenges and learn from failures, reinforcing the value of shared experiences. Our conversations also addressed member identity and the characteristics that

define them. We aim to attract motivated individuals willing to participate and exchange ideas. Embracing diversity of skills, backgrounds, and perspectives was recognised as critical to building trust and fostering innovation. In terms of values, participants emphasised openness, transparency, and inclusiveness. Encouraging members to share good/best practices and mistakes is vital to establishing credibility and promoting growth. Defining success is challenging, but the group discussion envisioned a sustainable community that encourages active participation. What makes it sustainable is its ability to maintain value, engagement, and knowledge sharing over the long term. Ideas such as mentorship and collaborative resource development like developing a pool of good practices align with established models seen in digital communities. Lastly, while the community's brand is still under discussion, participants recognised the value of clear communication and identity, and positioned members as "bridge builders" and guides in complex research environments. Overall, our Identity discussions highlight trust, shared purpose, and transparency as key drivers of success.

From the Community Canvas to Working Groups

The outcome of the Community Canvas process was the establishment of three dedicated working groups (WG), each addressing a key aspect of community development. The first group focuses on building a shared vision and strategy, ensuring that the community is aligned with national and institutional priorities while fostering long-term engagement. The second group is dedicated to developing "yellow pages" and communication channels, providing a structured way to connect data stewards across organisations, share expertise, and promote collaboration. Lastly, the third group concentrates on identifying and addressing challenges faced by data stewards, including organisational barriers, funding uncertainties, and evolving skill requirements. This group actually collects topics that can be considered as future areas of work and can be addressed by the community or specific working groups. These working groups will lay the foundations for a structured and effective network of data stewards that will allow for continuous exchange and co-ordinated action.

1. WG Vision and Strategy

The Strategy and Vision Working Group outlined the pillars for building a strategic, comprehensive, sustainable, and collaborative data steward community in Germany. By envisioning data stewardship as a strategic domain in research processes, the community aims to establish data stewards as critical assets in research, focusing on professionalising the role of data stewards and fostering collaboration within the community. The community's potential to drive significant progress in research data management lies in its long-term sustainability and in its engagement with national and international stakeholders and actors. Through these efforts, the community aims to influence policy development, promote the development of data stewardship across institutions, and support the ongoing development of data management practices.

Strategic Integration of Data Stewardship

The discussions also emphasise the importance of integrating data stewardship into the strategic planning of research institutions. The group advocates for data stewardship to become a core element of institutional governance and research infrastructure.. This is the fundamental basis for ensuring quality assurance policies and institutional alignment with research policy requirements, such as good scientific practice, open science, FAIR data, and reproducibility. This ensures that data is managed to support openness, transparency, and long-term usability. By strategically embedding data stewardship within institutional structures and its governance, the community aims to drive a cultural shift, making it an integral part of the research process rather than a bureaucratic burden.

Role of Data Stewards in Research Institutions

A central theme emerging from the group's discussions is the professionalisation of data stewardship. The working group advocates for positioning data stewards as integral members of research teams, emphasising the strategic importance of their roles in data management. This shift aims to transform the perception of data stewardship from a mere administrative task to a vital, value-driven research component. By advocating for clear roles and responsibilities, the community aims to empower data stewards and ensure they are supported within their organisations and the broader research ecosystem. This focus on professionalisation aligns with the growing recognition of data stewardship as essential for effective research data management and compliance with international standards.

Sustainability and Governance

The sustainability of the community is another critical outcome discussed by the group. While there is recognition of the need for formal governance structures to ensure accountability and alignment with the community's goals, the working group also advocates for flexibility and inclusivity. This balance between formal structure and informal engagement creates an environment where members can contribute freely while ensuring that the community operates efficiently and cohesively. At the DSgG, various governance models were discussed with their respective advantages and disadvantages, such as the establishment of an association, which would then be accompanied by financial resources, as well as the use of already established structures such as Forschungsdaten.org.

Fostering Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

The need for enhanced collaboration and knowledge sharing is another key outcome discussed by the working group. Establishing a platform for knowledge and experience exchanges and interactions is crucial for bridging the gaps between various data steward roles and profiles.

The community aims to facilitate this through workshops, webinars, and networking events, enabling participants to exchange knowledge, share good/best practices, and develop solutions to common challenges. In doing so, the community seeks to create an inclusive space where diverse perspectives can contribute to the continuous evolution of data

stewardship practices. Furthermore, through partnerships with organisations like the NFDI, DINI/nestor, Landesinitiativen¹⁴, Research Data Alliance (RDA) and CODATA, national and international collaboration will ensure that the community remains aligned with global trends and good/best practices.

2. WG Challenges

In the Challenges of data stewardship Working Group, participants systematically explored key issues shared across the data stewards. Several core challenges were identified such as defining the roles of data stewards, motivating researchers to engage in RDM, addressing legal and technical constraints, and improving infrastructure. The group also discussed initial solutions, including developing a knowledge base, establishing communication platforms, and fostering a collaborative support network. The role of data stewards is one of the main challenges, highlighting their relevance and heterogeneous responsibilities in supporting researchers, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, and advocating for open science. A key takeaway was the ongoing struggle to define and justify the position within institutions, leading to reflections on whether technical and advisory roles should be distinct or integrated. The working group also explored aspects of technical infrastructure through the case study on an RDM system used in materials science. This included testing and evaluating trade-offs between custom-built and existing solutions, focusing on technical complexity, user accessibility, and approaches to sustaining long-term researcher engagement. Across these discussions, the group recognised the need for continuous collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and institutional support to overcome persistent challenges in data stewardship.

3. WG Yellow Pages and Channels

This group aims to create a comprehensive platform for the data stewards community, facilitating communication, collaboration, and knowledge-sharing among professionals. The platform should be designed to be easily accessible and manageable, allowing data stewards at all levels to engage with resources, guidance, and insights on good/best practices in data stewardship. The platform could support knowledge sharing, professional development, and enhancement of the overall quality of data management practices in research. The platform could include the development of a community-driven "Yellow Pages," which could provide a curated directory of data stewards and relevant institutions across Germany. This directory should highlight the specific areas of expertise of various data stewards, making it easy for individuals and organisations to identify key contacts and collaborate effectively on data management initiatives. The goal could be to foster stronger connections within the community, ensuring that professionals could quickly find the right people and resources to address their specific needs. So far, the meetings have primarily focused on the technical aspects of reflecting on the platform requirements. These discussions are essential in aligning the group's objectives and ensuring that the platform meets the practical needs of data stewards. Moving forward, the focus might require further discussion on the requirements and

¹⁴ <https://forschungsdaten.info/fdm-im-deutschsprachigen-raum/deutschland/fdm-landesinitiativen-und-regionale-netzwerke/> (last check: 2025-07-21)

potentially deploying an early version platform to test whether it provides real, actionable value to its users.

Conclusion & Outlook

Since October 2022, a data steward community has been taking shape through the joint development of shared values, a common identity, and the sharing of experiences. A structure is emerging that includes roles such as buddies, ambassadors, community managers, and more. The identification of community needs during the DSgG 2024 was an important milestone in establishing a sustainable data steward community in Germany, that fosters long-term engagement, professional development, and knowledge sharing through clear roles, strategic collaboration, and institutional integration. The establishment of working groups highlights the value data stewards see in this joint community effort, and everyone is welcome to participate.

Dedicated working groups focusing on vision and strategy development, communication channels and yellow pages, as well as addressing challenges will strengthen the role of data stewards while fostering a collaborative environment where diverse perspectives can thrive. By creating spaces where data stewards feel valued and supported, this initiative is vital for advancing data stewardship in Germany, promoting effective research data management practices and contributing to the principles of open science. As the community continues to evolve, ongoing communication and adaptation will be necessary to meet emerging needs and challenges within the dynamic landscape of research data management.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their sincere thanks to all participants for their contributions and to TU9 and RWTH Aachen University for its financial and organisational support.

Literature

Hausen, D. A., Jaek, A., Kaulbach, L.-L., and Lennartz, T. (2024). Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024. Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024 (DSgG2024), Aachen. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14191227>

Hausen, D. A., Windeck, J., Schönau, S., and Dierkes, J. (2025). Results of the Community Canvas Sessions –Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024. Data Stewardship goes Germany 2024 (DSgG 2024), Aachen. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112753>

Jetten, M. (2021). Professionalising the data steward roles in the Netherlands. FAIR data stewardship capacity building & the role of communities. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5091300>

Jetten, M., Grootveld, M., Mordant, A., Jansen, M., Bloemers, M., Miedema, M., & Van Gelder, C. W. G. (2021). Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands. Competences, training and education. Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship (1.1). *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4623713>

Krause, M., Rümmler, A., Zinke, K., Little, J., and Würzner, K.-M. (2024). Data Stewardship goes Germany (DSgG), Dresden/Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10514268>

Oset García, P., Van den Eynden, V., Choueiki, Z., and Acar, T. (2023). Building a Community of Data Stewards in Flanders: Lessons Learned from the FRDN Knowledge Hub's Experience with the Community Canvas Framework. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10039571>.

Pfortmüller, F., Luchsinger, N., Mombartz, S. (2017). The Community Canvas Guidebook. The Guide to build meaningful communities. <https://community-canvas.org/>

RfII–Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen (2016), Herausgeber. Leistung aus Vielfalt: Empfehlungen zu Strukturen, Prozessen und Finanzierung des Forschungsdatenmanagements in Deutschland. 2016, <https://d-nb.info/1104292440/34>

Rothfritz, L. (2019). Data Stewardship als Boundary-Work. *edoc - Open-Access-Publikationsserver der Humboldt-Universität*. <https://doi.org/10.18452/20636>

Seidlmayer, E., Hoffmann, F., Dierkes, J., Lindstädt, B., Depping, R., Förstner, K.U. (2023). Forschung unterstützen – Empfehlungen für Data Stewardship an akademischen Forschungsinstitutionen: Ergebnisse des Projektes DataStew. *Publisso*. <https://repository.publisso.de/resource/fri:6441397>

Steinke, B., Hausen, D., Kuberek, M., Hora, M., Kessler, K., Kramer, C., ... Strötgen, R. (2022). Data Stewards an den TU9-Universitäten – Bestandsaufnahme, Handlungsfelder und Kooperationspotenzial. *Bausteine Forschungsdatenmanagement*, (1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2022.1.8364>

<https://forschungsdaten.info/fdm-im-deutschsprachigen-raum/deutschland/fdm-landesinitiativen-und-regionale-netzwerke/> (last check: 2025-07-21)

https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_steward (last check: 2025-03-24)